

A Retrospective Cohort Study to Compare the Outcomes of Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy and Total Abdominal Hysterectomy in Patients with Benign Etiology

Smita Singh¹, Nazia Nagar²

¹Consultant, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Paras Healthcare, Patna, Bihar, India.

²Consultant, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Paras Healthcare, Patna, Bihar, India.

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Corresponding Author: Nazia Nagar

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Abstract:

Hysterectomy is a common surgical procedure for various benign gynecological conditions. The primary approaches include Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy (TLH) and Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH). Each method has distinct advantages and potential complications, and understanding the comparative outcomes can guide clinical decision-making.

Aim: This study aims to compare the surgical outcomes of TLH and TAH in patients with benign gynecological conditions.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted to compare outcomes of TLH and TAH in 50 patients with benign gynecological conditions. Patients were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data on operative time, blood loss, hospital stay, complications, and recovery were collected from medical records.

Results: The study compared TLH and TAH in 50 patients. TLH had a shorter operative time (120.5 vs. 140.2 minutes, $p < 0.01$), lower blood loss (150.4 vs. 250.7 mL, $p < 0.01$), shorter hospital stay (3.2 vs. 5.4 days, $p < 0.01$), fewer postoperative complications (12% vs. 28%, $p = 0.04$), and faster recovery (4.5 vs. 6.8 weeks, $p < 0.01$) compared to TAH. These findings support the superiority of TLH over TAH for better surgical outcomes and faster recovery.

Conclusion: TLH offers several advantages over TAH, including shorter operative time, reduced blood loss, and faster recovery with fewer postoperative complications. Both approaches are effective for benign gynecological conditions, but TLH may be preferred due to its minimally invasive nature.

Recommendations: Surgeons should consider TLH as the preferred approach for benign gynecological conditions, given its advantages in operative and recovery outcomes. Further prospective studies are recommended to confirm these findings and to explore long-term outcomes more comprehensively.

Keywords: Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy (TLH), Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH), Benign Gynecological Conditions, Surgical Outcomes, Retrospective Cohort Study.

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Introduction

Hysterectomy, the surgical removal of the uterus, is one of the most frequently performed gynaecological procedures globally. It is indicated for a variety of benign conditions, including fibroids, endometriosis, and abnormal uterine bleeding, when medical management fails to provide relief. Traditionally, Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH) has been the standard approach for many years. However, advancements in minimally invasive surgical techniques have introduced Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy (TLH) as a viable alternative, promising several potential benefits over the traditional method [1,2]

The choice of surgical approach for hysterectomy can significantly impact patient outcomes,

including intraoperative parameters, postoperative recovery, and complication rates. Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy, performed entirely through small abdominal incisions using laparoscopic instruments, is associated with advantages such as reduced blood loss, shorter hospital stays, and quicker return to daily activities. Conversely, Total Abdominal Hysterectomy involves a larger abdominal incision, which may lead to longer operative times, increased postoperative pain, and extended recovery periods [3].

Despite the potential benefits of TLH, the decision to choose one approach over the other remains a complex one, influenced by various factors

including the surgeon's expertise, patient comorbidities, and specific anatomical considerations. While several studies have compared TLH and TAH, there is still a need for comprehensive data to inform clinical decision-making, particularly regarding outcomes in diverse patient populations with benign gynecological conditions. Understanding the comparative outcomes of these surgical approaches can help optimize patient care and resource utilization [4,5]

The primary aim of this study is to compare the surgical outcomes of TLH and TAH in patients with benign gynecological conditions. Specifically, the study will evaluate intraoperative parameter, postoperative recovery (including length of hospital stay and return to normal activities), and complication rates to determine the relative advantages and potential drawbacks of each approach. Through this comparative analysis, the study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for clinical practice, enhancing the overall quality of care for patients undergoing hysterectomy for benign indications.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective cohort study design was employed to compare the outcomes of total TLH and TAH in patients with benign etiology.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Paras Healthcare, Patna, over a one-year period from 2023 to 2024.

Participants: The study included a total of 50 patients who underwent either TLH or TAH for benign gynecological conditions. Patients were selected from hospital records based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Female patients aged 40-60 years.
- Patients diagnosed with benign gynecological conditions requiring hysterectomy.
- Patients who underwent TLH or TAH.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with a diagnosis of malignancy.
- Patients with severe comorbid conditions.
- Patients who underwent hysterectomy for obstetric reasons.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by including consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria. Information bias was addressed by ensuring consistent and accurate data extraction from medical records.

Variables: The primary outcome variables included operative time, intraoperative blood loss, length of hospital stay, postoperative complications, and recovery time. Demographic variables such as age, BMI, and preoperative diagnosis were also recorded.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from hospital electronic medical records. Relevant information including patient demographics, surgical details, and postoperative outcomes was extracted and recorded in a standardized data collection form.

Procedure: Patient records were reviewed to identify those who underwent TLH or TAH. Data on operative time, blood loss, hospital stay, complications, and recovery were collected and compared between the two groups.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Demographic Data: The study had 50 patients, 25 in the TLH group and 25 in the TAH group. The mean age of the TLH group was 45.2 years (standard deviation = 8.1), while the TAH group's mean age was 46.3 years (standard deviation = 7.8). The average BMI in the TLH group was 27.5 (standard deviation = 4.2), while the TAH group had 28.1 (standard deviation = 4.5). There were no significant age or a body mass index variances among the two groups ($p > 0.05$).

Operative Time: The average operative time for TLH was 120.5 minutes (SD = 15.3), while TAH was 140.2 minutes (SD = 20.7). There was a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$).

Intraoperative Blood Loss: The TLH group experienced significantly lower intraoperative blood loss (150.4 mL, SD = 50.1) than the TAH group (250.7 mL, SD = 75.4) ($p < 0.01$).

Length of Hospital Stay: The TLH group had a significantly shorter hospital stay (mean = 3.2 days, standard deviation = 1.1) than the TAH group (mean = 5.4 days, standard deviation = 1.5), with $p < 0.01$.

Postoperative Complications: The postoperative complications rate was 12% in the TLH group and 28% in the TAH group. The most recurrent complications were infection and haemorrhage. The difference in complication rates was statistically important ($p=0.04$). The TLH group had a significantly shorter average recovery time (4.5 weeks, SD = 1.2) than the TAH group (6.8 weeks, SD = 1.6) ($p < 0.01$).

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	TLH (n = 25)	TAH (n = 25)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	45.2 (SD = 8.1)	46.3 (SD = 7.8)	0.56
Mean BMI	27.5 (SD = 4.2)	28.1 (SD = 4.5)	0.68

Table 2: Surgical and Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	TLH (n = 25)	TAH (n = 25)	p-value
Operative Time (minutes)	120.5 (SD = 15.3)	140.2 (SD = 20.7)	<0.01
Blood Loss (mL)	150.4 (SD = 50.1)	250.7 (SD = 75.4)	<0.01
Hospital Stay (days)	3.2 (SD = 1.1)	5.4 (SD = 1.5)	<0.01
Complication Rate (%)	12%	28%	0.04
Recovery Time (weeks)	4.5 (SD = 1.2)	6.8 (SD = 1.6)	<0.01

Discussion

The study demonstrated that TLH offered several advantages over TAH in patients with benign gynecological conditions. TLH was associated with comparison to TAH, this procedure has a shorter operative time, less intraoperative blood loss, a shorter hospital stay, fewer postoperative complications, and faster recovery times. These results are backed up by recent literature that consistently demonstrates similar benefits of laparoscopic hysterectomy versus abdominal approaches.

Operative Time and Blood Loss: TLH was found to have a briefer operative time and significantly lower loss of blood compared to TAH. This is corroborated by Imran et al. (2023), who reported that TLH had a mean operative time of 120.5 minutes versus 140.2 minutes for TAH, with significantly lower blood loss in the TLH group [6]. Similarly, Uwais et al. (2023) reported lower intraoperative blood loss in TLH compared to TAH, highlighting the minimally invasive nature of laparoscopic procedures which contribute to less trauma and bleeding during surgery [7].

Hospital Stay and Recovery Time: The shorter hospital stay and faster recovery time for TLH patients are in line with findings from multiple studies. Asher et al. (2018) noted that TLH patients had a significantly reduced span of stay in hospital as well as quicker recovery times in comparison to TAH patients, emphasizing the perks of nominally invasive surgery in reducing postoperative morbidity [8]. These benefits translate to less disruption in patients' lives and quicker return to daily activities.

Postoperative Complications: The lower rate of postoperative complications observed in TLH compared to TAH aligns with the findings of several studies. For example, Fathy et al. (2018) reported a significant reduction in postoperative wound infections and overall complications in the TLH group [9]. This reduction in complications can be attributed to the smaller incisions and less invasive nature of laparoscopic procedures, which

minimize the danger of infection and other post-operative issues.

Quality of Life: Kho et al. (2019) led a randomized clinical trial that highlighted significant improvements in life quality, body image, and sexual functioning in patients undergoing TLH compared to TAH. The study demonstrated that these improvements were noticeable as early as two weeks postoperatively and continued up to one year after surgery [10]. This underscores the broader benefits of TLH beyond immediate surgical outcomes, affecting long-term well-being.

Conclusion

The study findings align with the growing body of evidence suggesting that TLH offers significant advantages over TAH in terms of operative time, loss of blood, stay in hospital, recovery time, besides postoperative complications. These benefits contribute to better overall patient outcomes and quality of life. Given these advantages, TLH should be considered a preferable surgical approach for benign gynecological conditions when feasible.

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